

Feature Based Sentiment Analysis Using Spacy & TextBlob

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Abstract—Research in the area of sentiment analysis and opinion mining has the potential to have a big impact on today's company. The demand for its autonomous analysis was sparked by an increase in consumer reviews. The bulk of sentiment analysis tools currently in use only distinguish between positive and negative polarities, making it difficult for other consumers to learn about the features that are being highlighted and for product manufacturers to fix the issues. Reviews are frequently quite vague and fail to mention the product's features. In the study, feature-based sentiment analysis was suggested, in which TextBlob is used to forecast the polarities of the features derived from the reviews.

Keywords: Feature-Based Sentiment Analysis, Sentiment Polarity, POS Tagging, TextBlob, Spacy.

I. INTRODUCTION

E-commerce is quickly rising to the top of the list of preferred shopping methods. Prior to purchase, the products are reviewed. It can be challenging for other buyers to find a thorough, unbiased evaluation of the product they want to purchase because there are many reviews for a product and the majority of those reviews don't define the product's qualities. The sentiment analysis based on the retrieved attributes and forecasting the relevant polarities will give customers and product makers better clarity on the features specified by customers. We will develop a very basic aspect-based sentiment analysis that can detect general concepts and comprehend the attitudes surrounding them.

Teams cannot manually sift through tens of thousands of tweets, customer care chats, or evaluations of products, especially if they wish to perform a thorough analysis of the data. Businesses can automatically evaluate enormous amounts of data in great detail thanks to aspect-based sentiment analysis, which also helps teams concentrate on more crucial activities and saves time and money.

Breakdown aspect-based sentiment analysis can extract:

- **Sentiments:** favourable or negative feedback regarding a certain element
- **Aspects:** the category, feature, or subject being discussed

II. RELATED WORKS

Recent years have seen a proliferation of research articles on sentiment analysis, opinion mining, and product reviews. Xing Fang and Justin Zhan carried the sentiment polarity

categorization in the study [1]. They classified the text's polarity as either positive, negative, or neutral.

The authors [2] used Aspect Sentiment Triple Extraction (ASTE). In order to indicate WHAT the targeted elements are, HOW their feeling polarities are, and WHY they have these polarities (or opinion reasons), the triplets (What, How, Why) are retrieved from the input sentence.

The developers [3] attempted to automate the reading of text from a large number of reviews. The superfluous information that is useless for sentiment analysis is removed. Words that are frequently used or stop words are carefully eliminated. In order to accomplish this, we used part-of-speech tagging (POS tagging) to accurately capture the review's true sentiment.

III. EXISTING & PROPOSED SYSTEM

Sentiment analysis is the method of determining if a text contains positive or negative sentiment.. Businesses frequently employ it to analyse social media data for sentiment, evaluate brand reputes, and comprehend clientele. Customer feedback about a product's usability directly affects future customer purchasing decisions, and unfavourable reviews result in revenue losses.[4] The majority of the time, the reviews are quite general and don't mention any specific product attributes. The majority of sentiment analysis systems in use today only categorise polarities as positive or negative because the reasons why customers make those comments are unknown, making it challenging for other customers to learn about the features being mentioned and for product manufacturers to easily address the problems.

The study proposes feature-based sentiment analysis, in which the reviews' features are retrieved, and TextBlob is used to forecast the polarities that match to those features.

The task of aspect-based sentiment analysis (ABSA) identifies and assigns sentiment to the aspects, features, and subjects that it has classified in the body of data. Compared to other methods that provide a more general picture of sentiment, ABSA's insights are more thorough and in-depth. [5]Topic-based sentiment analysis provides you with the sentiment for a specific topic in the data, as opposed to document-based sentiment analysis, which provides you with a clear answer based on specific keywords in a piece of text. A holistic perspective of the customer's attitudes toward

various parts of your product or service and brand is provided by ABSA thanks to enhanced characteristics of aspect-based sentiment analysis that let it extract granular information from the data.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

A. Part-Of-Speech (POS) Tagging

The first thing we want to do is divide our phrases into the target features (like food) and their sentiment descriptions (e.g. delicious).[6] Spacy, a Python library for natural language processing, will be used for this. In spacy, we use Tokenization, Part-Of-Speech(POS) Tagging, Dependency Parsing.

Tokenization: Text can be divided up into words, punctuation, etc.

Part-Of-Speech (POS) Tagging: Putting word kinds, such verb or noun, on tokens.

Dependency Parsing: Naming the syntactic dependencies that describe the connections between various tokens, such as subject and object.

Spacy's dependency parsing and the POS (Part-Of-Speech) tags allow us to see the dependency for each token inside our phrases. We're also paying attention to the child tokens, so that we're able to pick up intensifiers such as "very", "quite", and more.

#	TEXT	DEP	TEXT_POS	HEAD_TEXT	HEAD_POS	CHILDREN
1	The	det	DET	food	NOUN	[]
2	food	nsubj	NOUN	was	AUX	[The, had]
3	we	nsubj	PRON	had	VERB	[]
4	had	relci	VERB	food	NOUN	[we, yesterday]
5	yesterday	npadmov	NOUN	had	AUX	[]
6	was	ROOT	AUX	was	AUX	[food, delicious, .]
7	very	admov	ADV	delicious	ADJ	[]
8	delicious	acompl	ADJ	was	AUX	[very]
9	.	punct	PUNCT	was	AUX	[]

Fig1: POS Tagging Table

Fig 2: POS Tagging Graph Network

```

import spacy
nlp = spacy.load("en_core_web_sm")

[ ] sentences = [
    'The food we had yesterday was delicious',
    'The internet was slow.',
    'Our experience was suboptimal',
    'My time in Italy was very enjoyable',
    'I found the meal to be tasteless'
]

[ ] for sentence in sentences:
    doc = nlp(sentence)
    for token in doc:
        print(token.text, token.dep_, token.head.text, token.head.pos_,
              token.pos_, [child for child in token.children])
    
```

B. Extract Feature and Descriptive Term

In order to extract feature and descriptive term ,[7] analyze POS Tags and Dependency Parsing. Verify that the token.dep_ is "nsubj" and token.pos_ is "NOUN", if it is true then it is the feature of the sentence. (Nsubj : A nominal subject is a noun phrase which is the syntactic subject of a clause, NOUN : noun).

Verify that token_pos is 'ADJ', if it is true then it is descriptive_term of the feature. (ADJ : adjective)

To extract descriptive term with intensifiers, verify token.pos_ is 'ADV'. (ADV : adverb)

```

for sentence in sentences:
    doc = nlp(sentence)
    descriptive_term = ''
    for token in doc:
        if token.pos_ == 'ADJ':
            prepend = ''
            for child in token.children:
                if child.pos_ != 'ADV':
                    continue
                prepend += child.text + ' '
            descriptive_term = prepend + token.text
    print(sentence)
    print(descriptive_term)
    
```

```

aspects = []
for sentence in sentences:
    doc = nlp(sentence)
    descriptive_term = ''
    target = ''
    for token in doc:
        if token.dep_ == 'nsubj' and token.pos_ == 'NOUN':
            target = token.text
        if token.pos_ == 'ADJ':
            prepend = ''
            for child in token.children:
                if child.pos_ != 'ADV':
                    continue
                prepend += child.text + ' '
            descriptive_term = prepend + token.text
    aspects.append({'aspect': target,
                   'description': descriptive_term})
print(aspects)
    
```


VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this study, sample reviews are subjected to feature-based sentiment analysis. The most popular features are retrieved using Spacy,[10] the opinions relating to these features are extracted, and the degree of the polarity, whether positive or negative, is determined using TextBlob.

In the future, a more advanced and powerful dependency parser can be used that could also identify the negation words, For e.g, it may not pick up 'not' in 'not great'

VII. REFERENCES

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